

Complexometric Determination of Aluminium in its Ores and in Presence of Other Metal Ions Using 2-(2'-Lepidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-ammonium sulpho-nate (LANAS) as Indicator

(Miss) ADARSH KHOSLA, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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A complexometric method for the determination of aluminium with EDTA in the presence of iron, copper, cobalt, vanadium and titanium has been developed using 2-(2'-lepidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-ammonium sulpho-nate¹ (LANAS) as indicator. Back titrations using $ZnSO_4$ have been used and the colour change (orange to violet) at the end point is instantaneous and sharp.

ORES of aluminium, such as bauxite contain, besides aluminium, other elements such as iron, titanium, silicon, vanadium, etc. For determining aluminium in these ores an accurate and rapid method is required. Complexometric back-titrations using 2-(2'-lepidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-ammonium sulpho-nate (LANAS)¹ as indicator have been studied in the present work to meet this need. Back-titrations were preferred since boiling with excess of EDTA is necessary to chelate the aluminium quantitatively.

This work was carried out in several steps. Firstly the optimum conditions for an accurate determination of aluminium when present alone were determined. The effect of the presence of various foreign ions on this titration was studied and the maximum allowable quantity of each that can be present without impairing the accuracy of estimation of aluminium was determined. Next a method for the determination of aluminium in the presence of iron, copper, cobalt, titanium and vanadium which normally interfere, was developed. The method has been tested with preanalysed samples of bauxite.

Experimental

Reagents and Standard Solutions :

Metal ion solutions—A. R. grade samples of potash alum and zinc sulphate were used for making solutions of these cations in double distilled water which were made slightly acidic with H_2SO_4 and standardized using conventional methods.

EDTA Solution was prepared by dissolving the A. R. grade disodium salt in double distilled water and standardized against standard zinc sulphate solution using xylenol orange as indicator.

10% solution of hexamine buffer and 0.1% solution of (LANAS)¹ indicator were prepared.

Preliminary Investigations for titration conditions :

The effect of variables i.e. temperature, time of heating, pH range, indicator concentration, metal ion concentration and medium on the determination of aluminium metal have been examined and the optimum conditions are summarised below.

The pH range 6 to 7 was found to be most appropriate for a sharp end point colour change. Hexamine buffer was used to adjust the pH within this range. Effect of heating was studied and the best and most concordant results were got on heating the samples for 5 minutes. The amount of indicator added in each titration did not affect the reading (up to 1.0 ml of indicator was tried). Up to 0.027 mg of metal ion concentration could be determined quite accurately. Effect of change in medium was also studied. In non-aqueous media the end point colour change was rather slow.

Result and Discussion

Effect of diverse ions : In the determination of 0.27 mg/ml of aluminium, 50 mg/ml of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , SO_3^{2-} , $S_2O_8^{2-}$, acetate, tartrate, SCN^- , PO_4^{3-} and thiourea ; 10 mg/ml of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 5 mg/ml. of borate ; 0.5 mg/ml. of S^{2-} and citrate ; 8 mg/ml of Mg(II) and Sr(II), 2mg/ml of Ag(I), Ca(II) and Sb(III) and 0.2 mg/ml of Be(II) did not cause any interference.

Fluoride interferes very strongly and in presence of oxalate, even with 0.5 mg, the end point colour change is not very sharp. Fe(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Sn(II), Pb(II), Fe(III), La(III), Cr(III) and vanadyl interfere seriously. Hg(II) can be masked upto 4 mg. with I^- .

Recommended Procedure :

To a suitable aliquot containing 0.27 mg of aluminium add excess of EDTA and 1 to 2 ml of 10% hexamine buffer so that pH is in the range of 6.0–7.0. Make total volume to about 10 ml with water. Now, heat this solution to ensure quantitative complexation. Cool and add 1 to 2 drops of indicator solution. The colour of the solution is orange. Titrate the unused excess EDTA with standard zinc sulphate solution till the colour changes from orange to violet. The violet colour disappears on keeping, probably due to the Al-EDTA complex breaking in absence of excess EDTA.

Determination of aluminium in the presence of iron, copper, cobalt, titanium and vanadium :

Accurate results were obtained according to the above procedure when only aluminium was present. But the presence of any metal ions chelated by EDTA, at pH 6.0 to 7.0, such as ferric, cupric, cobalt etc. would give high results for aluminium. Thus this method needed to be modified. The masking effect of fluoride ion on aluminium (III) has been utilized in the estimation of aluminium in the presence of other ions. The modified procedure is as follows :

To the violet solution obtained after back titration of the excess of EDTA add sodium fluoride (for 1 mg of Al add 2.75 gm. of NaF). Keep the solution at about 90° for 20 minutes. Cool and then titrate the liberated EDTA against standard zinc sulphate solution to the same violet colour end point. The Zn(II) now consumed corresponds to the amount of aluminium and difference in volumes of zinc used gives the amount of the other metal ions.

Determination of aluminium in ores

Pre-analysed bauxite samples were taken and their aluminium content determined by the following procedure :

Weigh accurately about one gram of bauxite sample, previously dried at 105°, into a 250 ml beaker. Add

15 ml of Conc. HCl and 10 ml of Conc. HNO₃. Mix well and digest on a hot plate till all the nitrous fumes disappear. Add 20 ml of 1:1 H₂SO₄. Mix well and continue the digestion. Evaporate to fumes so that all chlorides and nitrates are removed completely. Cool and add 100 ml of water (double distilled). Digest on a hot plate till the salts have gone into solution and then filter through Whatman No. 40 filter paper. Wash till free from soluble matter with 3 to 5% H₂SO₄. Preserve the filtrate and transfer the residue alongwith the filter paper to a platinum crucible. Dry it, incinerate and then ignite till no trace of carbon is left. Now, fuse the residue with enough fusion mixture. Cool and extract with 10% H₂SO₄ and add to the filtrate preserved above. Filter off any precipitate of silica obtained. Make up the total volume to 250 ml and determine the amount of aluminium following the recommended procedure. The results are shown in table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ALUMINIUM IN BAUXITE

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃ % present	Al ₂ O ₃ % found	% error
1.	48.25	48.01	0.49
2.	55.00	54.59	0.74
3.	47.05	46.88	0.36
4.	48.80	48.68	0.25

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Reference

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